

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 4.5

Demo 1: Cost reduction and data conflation in monitoring land change II

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This deliverable reports on the work conducted by the four pilots within the urban landscape dynamics theme in LandSense.focusing on cost reduction and data conflation in monitoring land change. This report follows up on D4.1.
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Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the activities across the four demonstration pilots within Demo 1: Cost reduction and data conflation in monitoring land change while highlighting the respective target groups, type of data collected, methods of data collection, approaches towards data conflation as well as in their contribution to citizen engagement. Data from three of the four pilots are already openly accessible and available in [Zenodo](#).

In addition, the pilots can be categorized into two main groups: the ones that focus on engagement with the broad public with a rather low-threshold approach (i.e. Vienna, Amsterdam) and the other two pilots (Toulouse and Heidelberg) that focus on an expert-oriented approach with dedicated mapathons.

One main topic of this report is data conflation, which was the primary focus of the Toulouse pilot, where data from IGN-FRANCE was commented on and validated by users and - after a quality check – went directly into the databases of IGN-FRANCE and local authorities.

Additionally, the deliverable provides an overview on the broad range of activities to get users onboard and to make their engagement as sustainable as possible. The most successful approaches to engage citizens were in the Heidelberg and the Toulouse pilots via mapathons and for the Vienna and the Amsterdam pilots, press releases and announcements via media were effective. In the last months of the project, opportunities for continued sustainability of the pilots will be explored.

1 Introduction

The demonstration cases of LandSense show how citizens can be involved in monitoring land change in urban and peri-urban areas, with an emphasis on land take, greenspace and landscape perception. This report describes the iterative processes and preliminary results for the real-life demonstration cases in WP4, based on the engagement action plans ([D2.2](#), [D2.3](#)) and the first round of pilot implementation ([D4.1](#)). The report will include experiences and lessons learned regarding the target groups and how to get users on board during the respective reporting period. Additionally, the “Urban Landscape Dynamics” pilots have an emphasis on cost reduction and data conflation.

The results of this deliverable are referring to the Theme “Urban Landscape Dynamics” and its pilots:

- City of Vienna
- City of Amsterdam
- City of Heidelberg
- City of Toulouse and surrounding areas

Each of the pilots is supported by one or more technical tools as shown in the following overview:

Pilot Area	Kind of tool	Name of tool	Main target group(s)
City of Vienna	Mobile application	CityOases	Citizens of Vienna, City of Vienna, environmental organisations, schools and young people (in former reporting period also: students)
City of Amsterdam	Mobile application	Mijn Park	City of Amsterdam ((in former reporting period also: Users of the park)
City of Heidelberg	Web Application	OSMlanduse validation	Students and academics for data production and anyone for data usage
City of Toulouse and surrounding areas	Web Application and Mobile Application	Paysages web and Paysages mobile	IGN-production department, Urban Planning Agency in Toulouse, master students, engineer students, researchers

Table 1 Overview on tools and target groups in pilot areas

Structure of the report

Similar to the previous report each pilot description begins with an update of the storyline. This storyline is a quick overview written in a way that should be attractive to the selected target group (e.g. broad public, young people, administration) and mostly a mixture between teasers and background information.

The next section elaborates on the different target groups of each pilot. The target groups were first defined in a previous report ([D2.2 Engagement action plans and campaign strategies for LandSense demonstration cases](#)). An update of the activities with the target groups shows if there were changes of the selected groups and outlines the experiences - barriers as well as helping factors – in communicating and cooperating with the target groups.

Then the report will explicitly show which steps were undertaken to reach the following goals:

- Conflation of citizen contributions on LULC and land change (both actively collected and passively mined) into authoritative databases
- Cost reduction in professional surveying and/or increase in available LULC data that could not be collected within current budgets of public bodies
- Open access to improved public information on land take and land change

The section “engagement strategies” explains the steps undertaken to create awareness of the campaign and to get volunteers and users on board. All pilots need sustainability of the engagement of the users. Therefore, activities to give feedback to users and to engage the over a longer time are made explicit.

A presentation of the app/website/prototype is the focus of the next section. If applicable technical and content related changes during reporting time are explained.

It is followed by an overview of the current and planned uptake and performance (table of key performance indicators).

2 Urban Landscape Dynamics - Demonstration Pilots

2.1 City of Vienna

Updated storyline

Objective: Complement local administration urban planning processes by gaining insights and data from citizens about the usage and perceptions of urban green and open spaces.

Tool: [City Oases mobile app](#) (previously known as Frei.Raum.Netz), publicly available since March 2019.

Lead: UBA

Key Stakeholders: City of Vienna (urban development and urban planning department – MA18), Vienna University of Technology, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences

For the ‘Urban LandScape Dynamics’ theme we developed an app that makes it possible for users to express their perception on and highlight their activities in Vienna urban open spaces and to search for those elements that other users contributed. The app is centred on finding and evaluating ‘City Oases’ – the ideal places to hang out in an urban environment. Users are encouraged to evaluate pre-set points or alternatively any other location they would like to share with their fellow citizens – in the app and on social media. Fellow citizens profit from their engagement as the collected ratings are instantly available for all app users.

The heart of the data collection is the subjective perception of the places and the activities that can be conducted. The locations are illustrated and documented by pictures of the surrounding in all cardinal directions. Further questions are related to the suitability of a broad range of possible activities and “well-being” factors e.g. cool spaces in summer. Different themes like e.g. the adaptation to a changing urban climate throughout a year can be quantified by various campaigns. Ideally this will provide the LandSense team – and stakeholders – with information regarding land cover (via the images) and land use (via activities/subjective feelings), as well as the state and setup of the area over a long period of time. Entities like the Urban Planning Department in the City of Vienna can use the data to improve their urban green and open spaces.

The app has been designed with up-scaling in mind – ready for multilingual use and with a set of activities and subjective feelings that fits almost every city. While in Vienna the pre-set quest points focus mainly on the Frei.Raum.Netz and the city parks – providing the Magistrate 18 of the City of Vienna with vital information about the perception of one of the most important development features – other cities are free to define their own areas of interest.

Target Groups - update

The City Oases app was developed with inputs from a range of stakeholders including, the Technical University of Vienna, the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, and the City of Vienna (urban development and urban planning dept). The app was co-developed by IIASA, UBA and G2K. IIASA is the lead

technical developer, UBA led the stakeholder consultations and G2K was responsible for the dissemination and communication. The target groups for the City Oases app are outlined in Table 2.

Table 2 Target groups: Vienna, in italic target groups of former reporting periods

Target groups	Experiences, barriers, helping factors
Citizens of Vienna	<p>Citizens of Vienna as well as tourists have been invited to download the app and get started. Users can search for specific activities and visit one of the points indicated on the map and additionally this point. User can also create and evaluate a new point and add it to the data pool – their current location for example (as long as its outdoors and openly accessible).</p> <p>They will be asked to rate characteristics like noise, cleanliness or attractiveness of the area and can name which activities can be done there. Finally, the users will be asked to take a few pictures and share the data with others.</p> <p>The ratings submitted by the citizen scientists will be shared with other users of the app so that they are able to access other people’s recommendations and ratings. Additionally, the anonymised collected data will be released as open data to the public including other scientists, researchers, students and the city council.</p> <p>A specific heat wave campaign was implemented in mid-July which was well promoted across Austrian news agencies.</p>
City of Vienna	<p>MA18 is satisfied that their icons of activities could be used in the app and that they will receive the pictures collected by the app. Public relation activities, together with the City of Vienna administration, included participation in the “Forum Öffentlicher Raum“in spring 2019. Contact with the City of Vienna are ongoing.</p>
Environmental Organisations	<p>Global 2000 promotes the app via their communication channels, made a video about the app and is currently actively involved in planning the further roll-out activities. Global2000 has also good contacts to other environmental NGOs that will be used to increase the awareness of the app beyond a broad range of people.</p> <p>Promotional video created by G2K: https://youtu.be/B34LbBBQ7pY</p>
School children and youths	<p>A new target group of CityOases now includes pupils and youths. This target group was mainly involved via the “Citizen Science Award 2019”, the “Forschungsfest 2019” and the “Aktionstage Nachhaltigkeit 2019”</p>
<i>5th semester architecture students of Vienna University of Technology</i>	<p>Students were a key target group for the 1st test run of the app.</p>
<i>5th semester landscape planning students of University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna</i>	<p>These students participated in a test run of the app that was integral part of improving the application.</p>

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

- The City Oases app was developed with inputs from a range of stakeholders including, the Technical University of Vienna, the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, and the City of Vienna (urban development and urban planning dept). The app was co-developed by IIASA, UBA and G2K. IIASA is the lead technical developer, UBA led the stakeholder consultations and G2K was responsible for the dissemination and communication.
- The app was first used by students, where some 180+ participants visited approximately 500+ locations in the city of Vienna. UBA collected feedback from the students to further refine the application prior to a public rollout in May, 2019.
- On May 17, 2019 the City Oases app was publicly launched within the event “Forum Public Spaces Vienna” at the workshop “Connecting public green spaces in real and in digital”. This activity was performed in the Stadtpark in cooperation between the city administration, UBA and Global 2000, with accompanying press releases from Global 2000 and UBA (1 joint press release, 1 article in one of the main Austrian newspapers “Heute”)
- A specific heat wave campaign was implemented in mid-July which was well promoted across Austrian news agencies (Austrian TV Station ORF, the radio stations Ö1, Radio Wien, Radio Niederösterreich and KroneHitRadio, as well as print and online versions of newspapers, and local free newspapers/online-media.
- City Oases is participating in the Citizen Science Award which focuses on promoting citizen science among schools across Austria. The award ceremony for the Citizen Science Awards will be held on 19.11.2019. This activity is led by UBA
- Approximately 2500 installs, 857 visited points, 1500 photos collected in summer 2019 campaign

- ➔ Conflation of citizen contributions on LULC and land change (both actively collected and passively mined) into authoritative databases

UBA and MA18 cooperated to attract users through the “Forum am Park”, a stakeholder conference involving the main actors within the City of Vienna administration and related institutions concerned with planning and the environment plus invited guests from academia and business. In addition, UBA offered training sessions for MA 18 employees on the use and functionality of the CityOases app.

IIASA provided MA18 with a link to download the pictures collected in the test runs. MA18 will use these pictures in their own internal system and does not plan to hand them over to anyone else.

Well prepared and anonymized data might be passed on to the district level (in total 23 districts in Vienna), this requires more single data contributions, so the main activities were focused on involving more users and collecting a higher number of contributions by citizens.

- ➔ Cost reductions in professional surveying and/or increase in available LULC data that could not be collected within current budgets of public bodies

Integration of data into the Frei.Raum.Netz Vienna: The City of Vienna has a keen interest in further developing and improving the green space network and has to consider the distribution of urban green spaces, the diversity of surfaces and differences concerning the quality. Also, for the currently quite dense

green space network the barrier free access of persons with restricted mobility will be enhanced and different target groups with their specific needs will be taken into consideration. The overall goal is that every Viennese citizen will be able to reach the closest segment of the open space network within a distance of approx. 250m. For further improvement the City Planning Department of the City of Vienna (MA 18 -Stadtentwicklung und Stadtplanung) is missing data and information on land cover as well as how people perceive and use open spaces.

For MA 18 the activities taken in context of LandSense are like a user survey of the broad public and bring in an additional aspect to their expert's view, which would exceed the MA18 budget. Especially photos made in different seasons can be used for additional insights. Integration of data into the next urban development plan [STEP 2025](#) – an improvement of this planning instrument that could not happen within their restricted budgets. The app and the results are helpful to refine and complement planning instruments to increase living quality in cities by gaining more relevant data and georeferenced photos.

➔ Open access to improved public information on land take and land change

The collected data (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3695015>) is freely available in the LandSense Zenodo Community repository.

➔ Engagement strategies within the reporting period (steps undertaken to create awareness of the campaign including timeline)

- 05.2018: Test campaign with architectural students from Vienna University of Technology
- 05.2018 - 07.2018: 2nd test campaign with students from University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences in Vienna
- 03.2019 - 07.2019: Engagement with Global 2000 activists for app testing and feedback
- 05.2019: Official public launch of City Oases within the event “Forum Public Space” in cooperation between the city administration MA18, Global 2000 and accompanying press releases from Global 2000 and Umweltbundesamt
- 05.2019 – 07.2019: Participation in the Citizen Science Award with its special target group of pupils and school classes. The award ceremony for the Citizen Science Awards will be held on 19.11.2019
- 07.2019 – 08.2019: Heat wave campaign focusing on identifying cool spots in the city
- Note: In addition to targeted campaigns a host of singular events were attended to promote City Oases (i.e. Actions day for Sustainable Development on 04.06.2019 and Austria Research Festival on 27.09.2019)

The activities are described in further detail in the next section.

05.2019 - “Forum Öffentlicher Raum“ <https://www.kommraus.wien/2019/forum-im-park>

On May 17, 2019 the City Oases app was publicly launched within the event “Forum Public Spaces Vienna” at the workshop “Connecting public green spaces in real and in digital”. This activity was performed in the Stadtpark in cooperation between the city administration, UBA and Global 2000, with accompanying [press](#)

[releases](#) from Global 2000 and UBA (1 [joint press release](#), [1 article](#) in one of the main Austrian newspapers “Heute”)

Figure 1: Launch of CityOases app at the Forum Öffentlicher Raum (© Stickler/Umweltbundesamt)

05.2019 - Participation in the Citizen Science Award

The Citizen Science Award with its special target group of pupils and school classes was open from 2nd May to 5th July (the award ceremony for the Citizen Science Awards was on 19th November 2019). The most committed citizen scientists, who are actively involved in one of the Citizen Science Award projects during the research period, will receive joint awards from the Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research and the research institutions at a festive ceremony.

In the past five years, the award has inspired almost 14,000 schoolchildren as well as citizens for research. Through their active participation, they have made a decisive contribution to 35 research projects in recent years. CityOases was one of the projects for 2019 and benefited from the PR activities with the award.

07.2019 - Heat wave Campaign, “CityOases shows you the coolest places in Vienna”

When Vienna faced a severe heat wave in summer 2019 our media work was well received by many newspapers, both free – subway tabloids as well as the serious expensive newspapers. The response was higher than expected. A joint press release of UBA and Global 2000 resulted in high level media coverage by two the [Austrian TV Station ORF](#) (2), the radio stations Ö1, Radio Wien, Radio Niederösterreich and KroneHitRadio (4), as well as print and online versions of [newspapers](#) (2) and local free newspapers/online-media (3).

Production of a CityOases promotional video

G2K produced a film to show to citizens how the app works. The film can be downloaded here: <https://www.apa-ots-video.at/video/0f1381d4cf1b4b779381d4cf1b7b77e9>

09.2019 - Forschungsfest Niederösterreich

The [Research Festival](#) took place on September 27, 2019 at the Palais Niederösterreich with free admission. Scientific institutions presented themselves at numerous stations, including City Oases. Science and research were explained in an understandable and entertaining way with show experiments, hands-on experiments

and show acts. To attract interest the CityOases team engaged with visitors in games (Mainly with the card deck) and awarded the winners with small prizes.

Figure 2: The CityOases station at the Forschungsfest 2019 (© Umweltbundesamt)

11.2019 - Citizen Science Day 2019

With a festive event on November 19, 2019 at the University of Vienna, the most committed citizen scientists were awarded attractive prizes by the BMBWF, the OeAD and the representatives of the research institutions. School classes could look forward to up to € 1,000 for the class cash desk. This year, a special prize of 2,000 euros was also awarded for the most creative video. Two Viennese school classes ([Wiedner Gymnasium / Sir Karl Popper Schule](#) and the [BRG 14 Linzer Straße](#)) won a citizen science award due to their activities in context of CityOases. A third school made a film about their involvement with the app.

Figure 3: The Citizen Science Award – winners using the CityOases app (©Banko/Umweltbundesamt)

The City Oases card deck

Using the data generated by the app, we compiled a simple card game. Based on the data collected with the CityOases app an offline game designed around the park landscape in Vienna. The values on the playing cards

are in relation to the rankings of the sites concerned by users. The data and images come from our users, so this game is also a successful example of using data entries. This card game was used at the Forschungsfest.

City Oases

Von der Citizen Science App zum Kartenspiel

www.cityoases.eu

Auf Basis der mit der CityOases App gesammelten Daten wurde ein Offline Spiel rund um die Parklandschaft in Wien entworfen. Die Werte auf den Spielkarten sind Momentaufnahmen vom Zeitpunkt der Spielentwicklung. Die Daten und Bilder stammen von unseren Nutzern, somit ist auch dieses Spiel ein erfolgreiches Beispiel für Citizen Science Initiativen.

Mit unseren Spielkarten kann man sowohl Quartett als auch Top Trumpf spielen und dabei die schönsten Orte der 23 Wiener Gemeindebezirke kennenlernen.

Quartett
Mischen Sie die Karten und teilen Sie die Karten im Uhrzeigersinn an jeden Mitspieler aus. Der Kartenstapel wird komplett verteilt. Der Spieler, der links neben Ihnen dem Kartengeber sitzt, beginnt. Dieser fragt einen anderen beliebigen Spieler nach einer Karte, die ihm zu einem Quartett fehlt. Sie dürfen nur nach einer Karte fragen, wenn Sie von dem betreffenden Quartett schon mindestens eine Karte in der Hand halten. Der gefragte Spieler muss dem Frager die Karte abgeben, wenn er diese auf der Hand hat. Der Frager ist solange weiter am Zug, bis ein Spieler die gewünschte Karte nicht hat. Dieser Spieler übernimmt dann das Fragen. Sobald ein Spieler ein volles Quartett auf der Hand hat, legt er es offen auf den Tisch. Wer keine Karten mehr in der Hand hat, wartet bis zum Ende des Spiels ab. Es gewinnt der Spieler mit der höchsten Anzahl an Quartetten.

Top Trumpf Stärkespiel kurz für 2 Spieler
Mischen Sie die Karten und legen sie zwei Stapel vor sich ab. Alle Spielenden einigen sich auf eine Kategorie, dann wird die oberste Karte abgehoben. Die Karte mit dem höheren Wert gewinnt. Der Spieler, der sie ausgespielt hat, erhält beide Karten. Das Spiel ist gewonnen, wenn man am meisten Karten erhalten hat.

Top Trumpf Stärkespiel lang
Mischen Sie die Karten und teilen Sie jedem Spielenden 7 Karten aus. Der Spieler, der links neben Ihnen (dem Kartengeber) sitzt, beginnt. Der erste Spieler nennt eine Kategorie und spielt eine Karte aus. Nun müssen die anderen Spieler versuchen diese Kategorie mit eigenen Karten zu übertreffen. Die Karte mit dem höheren Wert gewinnt. Der Spieler, der sie ausgespielt hat erhält alle Karten. Das Spiel ist gewonnen, wenn man am meisten Karten erhalten hat.

This work was supported by the EU-funded H2020 LandSense project under Grant Agreement 689812.

Figure 4: Playing instructions for the card game

Overview of app/prototype - technical and content related changes during reporting time

In the reporting period no main technical or content related changes were done, with the exception of the roll-out concerning cool places in the city. From the user's perspective, this is an app where they can find and share their favourite spots to hang out or for recreational activities.

Possible activities:

- Search for a suitable spot

Figure 5: Searching for a suitable spot

The app-users can search for places where they can do certain activities, or for spots that were highly rated by other people. The app will give an overview over previous ratings regarding perception and activities.

- Evaluate a pre-set Quest-Point
- Add additional/new Point

When adding a new point, the users can select the location themselves; otherwise they will be directed to an existing quest-point. They are then guided through a questionnaire and asked to take pictures of the area. The questionnaire focuses on subjective perception, nature and activities. At the end of the quest the app will encourage users to take another picture or Selfie and share it via Social Media using hash tags that reference the app and the project.

Figure 6: Completing a quest

Their observations will then be available to other users via the map or search function.

Uptake & Performance Measures

Table 3 Key Performance Indicators: Vienna

	Up to now	Planned
Number of installs	2315	500 +
Number of testers/users	262	500+
Number of observations	1332	Enough to generate a Map of Attractiveness / Emotion-map
Points covered by user	7,6 (average)	>5 per user
Photos	1500	
Media mentions	12	15

* includes the TU test where 1 user ~ team of 3

Figure 7: Distribution of locations visited by volunteers during the 2019 City Oases campaign

2.2 City of Amsterdam

Updated storyline

Objective: Test new methods of obtaining location specific information on subjective perception and preferences for urban green space and assess how this information can inform sustainable urban development.

Tool: [Mijn Park mobile application](#)

Lead: VUA

Key Stakeholders: City of Amsterdam

City-dwellers are realizing the benefits of green spaces and are flocking to urban parks. City planners face the challenge of ensuring that urban green spaces are functional for all citizens. To make informed choices they need the right information and that is where the Mijn Park app can help. Research shows that when considering the social functions of urban green spaces, quality is just as important as quantity. It is easy enough to map how much green spaces there are, but how do we measure their quality? How do city planners ensure that the city's green areas are attractive, accessible and inclusive – for everyone?

The Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VUA) in collaboration with the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA) developed Mijn Park, a mobile application that will help city planners do just that. As part of the LandSense Citizen Observatory, the ‘Mijn Park’ (My Park) app asks respondents to go to several locations in a park and give subjective responses to those locations. They are then further questioned about how they use the whole park and how much they would like to see certain changes made in the park. This information provides information that can help to inform decisions about any renovations or improvements to the park.

A pilot campaign was conducted in the summer of 2018 in Rembrandt park in Amsterdam and insights from the citizen-driven observations were shared with the Department of Planning and Sustainability of Amsterdam. The pilot was very successful and project managers across the City of Amsterdam have been requesting more information and inquiring whether they can also use the app. Therefore, plans are being made for incorporating lessons learned from the pilot and expanding the use of the app to make it even more useful to informing xspatial planning and decision making.

Target Groups – update

The key target groups for the Amsterdam demonstration pilot are Rembrandtpark users and the City of Amsterdam.

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

- The input from 300 park users (150 via app, 150 via surveys) was used to prepare maps of subjective values in the park. The textual inputs provided by the respondents were also collated and clustered.
- This information was used to compile a report to the City of Amsterdam about how they perceive and use the park. This allowed the landscape architects to identify specific locations or issues that were priorities for improvement.
- The information was very useful to the municipality whereby the researchers at the VU have received numerous requests from the City of Amsterdam regarding possibilities to use a similar app for other projects.
- In the report we identified several locations in the park that were priorities for improvement. For example, there were a number of sites considered as unsafe, and two that were besides unsafe also unattractive, not relaxing and noisy. These sites would not have been identified by other measures. In addition, the textual inputs by respondents were found very interesting to the park managers.
- The results and reflection on the app were presented to a meeting of green space managers at the City of Amsterdam.
- Two scientific papers: One comparing the response via the app to that with surveys. The other comparing perception stated via the app to assumed perceptive information that can be won via social media or observations. Both almost completed.
- Meetings with 3 different City of Amsterdam project managers to discuss potential applications of 2nd iteration of app.
- Initial discussions with a community organization about application of the app and method in a grass-roots initiative.

- ➔ Conflation of citizen contributions on LULC and land change (both actively collected and passively mined) into authoritative databases

This pilot was viewed as a demonstrator and the contributions have not been added directly to the authoritative databases. We did provide a report with maps and an overview of text input to the relevant project managers at the City of Amsterdam. The report can be accessed [here](#) (in Dutch). The maps of subjective values in the park were used to inform decisions about where to prioritise renovations. For example, the locations that were unsafe were identified as priorities for improvement. Text inputs from the app were added to inputs received during neighbourhood workshops and by email, clustered according to the basic planning principles being used and entered into a ‘thoughts-rose.’

Figure 8: 'Thoughts-rose' of text input from Mijn Park app, as well as other participatory activities organised by the City of Amsterdam

- ➔ Cost reductions in professional surveying and/or increase in available LULC data that could not be collected within current budgets of public bodies

The app succeeded in engaging a group of park users that the City of Amsterdam usually cannot reach. This was especially younger people, aged 20-39, who were overrepresented amongst app respondents. This age

group are usually underrepresented in the usual public participation activities undertaken by the City. The app was viewed as a cost-savings approach because it did not need the extensive advertising and communication campaigns the city usually conducts to reach this group (often still unsuccessfully).

→ Open access to improved public information on land take and land change

The collected data (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3688392>) is freely available in the LandSense Zenodo Community repository. Visualisation of the results were provided to the public by way of a dedicated website (<https://mijnpark.environmentalgeography.nl/>).

Engagement strategies within the reporting period (steps undertaken to create awareness of the campaign including timeline)

As the campaign was completed, the focus in this reporting period was on visualisation and communication of results to stakeholders.

- 05.2018 – 09.2018: A demonstration pilot was conducted in Rembrandt park in Amsterdam with the Mijn Park app
- 01.2019: Publication of results on website; presentation to City of Amsterdam, Rembrandtpark project team.
- 01.2019 – 06.2019: Social media posts and interaction with comments regarding results (<https://twitter.com/MijnPark>)
- 03.2019 – 06.2019: Collaboration with Art Academy students to produce art pieces that reflect the app (See Figure 9).
- 06.2019: The team attended a neighbourhood meeting where the City of Amsterdam and presented their plans for the Rembrandtpark. The app results were presented.
- 11.2019: Presentation of app and results to entire parks team of City of Amsterdam

Figure 9: Flyer describing video made by one of the Art academy students.

The artists used the photos taken by people in the app to define a colour palette, and other responses in the app to create the contour. See <https://www.jewellerydepartment.nl/cactus-pig-mondriaan-and-spider/> for more information.

Overview of app/prototype - technical and content related changes during reporting time

The Mijn Park app can be used on a smartphone with GPS. The app brings users to specific locations in the park to question them about their preferences regarding that specific location. The app was developed for iOS and Android operating systems. Adapted from the FotoQuest Go app at IIASA, the content required for this research was designed and provided by researchers at the VUA to the app developers at IIASA.

A respondent using the Mijn Park app is directed to three different locations in the park (randomly selected from 30 potential locations) and asked a set of (the same) questions about each specific location. The location questions were based on literature on perception and preferences of green spaces. The asked how the respondent experienced the location (for example: how relaxing do you find this location?), how satisfied the respondent was with aspects of the landscape (for example: how satisfied are you with the number of trees on this location?) and how satisfied they were with maintenance of the location (for example: how satisfied are you with the maintenance of facilities on this location?). After the third location they were asked a set of questions about the whole park. These questions included questions about their preferences for changes to be made in the park (for example: how much do you think that BBQs need to be regulated in the park?) and how satisfied they were with aspects of the whole park (for example: how satisfied are you with availability of playgrounds?). Answers were given on Likert scale 1-5 (or 1-10) with a moveable scale bar. To finalise their response they were requested to answer some questions about their personal characteristics (for example: how old are you?; but also: how nature-oriented are you?) and then to register in order to upload their results.

Figure 10: Screenshots of the MijnPark mobile application used to collect subjective impressions of or Rembrandtpark users in Amsterdam

Uptake & Performance Measures

Table 4 Key Performance Indicators: Amsterdam

	Up to now	Planned
Number of installs	796	500 +
Number of testers/users	154	500+
Number of observations	377	100+
Points covered by user	3	3
Media mentions	3	5
Social media numbers	134 followers	150+
Website page visits	2,203 (1,761 unique page views)	2000+

Figure 11: Distribution of locations visited by volunteers during the 2018 MijnPark campaign in Rembrandtpark

2.3 City of Toulouse and its surrounding areas

Updated storyline

Objective: Evaluate how contributions from interested experts (i.e. public authorities, engineering students, etc.) can be integrated with the French Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) authoritative database

Tools: [Paysages mobile application](#), [Paysages web application](#) and [LACO-Wiki](#)

Lead: IGN-FRANCE

Key Stakeholders: Urban Planning Agency - Toulouse, Territorial Departmental Direction of Toulouse (31), Regional Direction of IGN (South Wes, Engineering Schools of IGN-France (ENSG), University of Toulouse.

The French National Mapping Agency (Institut National de l'Information Géographique et Forestière - IGN) is responsible for producing and maintaining the spatial data sets for all of France. At the same time, they must satisfy the needs of different stakeholders who are responsible for decisions at multiple levels from local to national. IGN produces many different maps including detailed road networks and land cover/land use maps over time. The information contained in these maps is crucial for many of the decisions made about urban planning, resource management and landscape restoration as well as other environmental issues in France. Recently, IGN has started the process of creating a high-resolution land use land cover (LULC) maps, aimed at developing smart and accurate monitoring services of LULC over time. To help update and validate the French LULC database, citizens and interested stakeholders can contribute using the Paysages mobile and web applications. This approach presents an opportunity to evaluate the integration of citizens in the IGN process of updating and validating LULC data.

The goal of the Toulouse pilot is to collect information in order to update authoritative LULC data. Contributors carry out the following two tasks:

- Distinguish between commercial, industrial and residential classes: for each aggregated class US235, choose a new class: industrial (US2), commercial (US3) or residential (US5).
- Validate changes detected by the LandSense Change Detection Service: for each new detected construction (having the types industrial, infrastructure and residential), the contributor should validate the change and the type of construction.

To validate the changes or to classify the urban classes, first a certain number of features are selected. Then, the features are visualised by using both the mobile and the web applications are used. The actual LU class in 2016 and 2019 was determined via photo interpretation of fine spatial resolution (20-50 cm) Orthophotos for each highlighted features. To explore the effect of interpreter variations on the reference data set, validation data from six different groups of interpreters were obtained in a series of mapathons. In each mapathon, the data sets and tools were introduced to participants at the beginning, along with a summary of the project's aims. IGN staff was also available to provide assistance during the mapathons. Each mapathon involved a different group of contributors; no mapathon had mixed contributions.

Target Groups – update

Table 5 Target groups: Toulouse

Target groups	Experiences, barriers, helping factors
Experts in LULC from the local authorities (AuAT)	Experts in LULC data from the Urban Planning Agency in Toulouse. They have good knowledge of LULC classification, aerial photograph-interpretation and geographic data mapping, but few have knowledge of remote sensing.
Research experts in LULC working at the research department of IGN-France (LASTIG)	Research experts in LULC data, map classification and change validation. These contributors were aware of the applied LandSense change detection algorithms.
Surveyors from the production department of IGN	This group comprised surveyors from the production department of IGN. They are rather experts in mapping topographic data (not LULC data).
First year students of the National Engineering in GIS School (ENSG)	This group attended a brief training event on aerial photograph-interpretation comprising a 1-hour lecture and 2-hour training session on aerial photograph interpretation. For this group, the contribution was included as part of their formal curriculum in order to apply skills related to aerial photograph-interpretation. This group comprised 60 students, and while not experts in LULC data, they would have received a semester of training in geographic science.
Students from the Masters degree in geographical information science (GIS) at ENSG	The contribution was part of their curriculum and the data collected were used further in their practical work. These students had, as part of their curriculum, already studied remote sensing, spatial classification and spatial data validation before taking part in experience. Of the 19 students, some also had experience in aerial photograph-interpretation. However, these students are not experts in LULC data.
First year students of ENSG who have not received training in aerial photograph-interpretation	This group consisted of a set of 15 student volunteers, who had begun their one-month curriculum in geographic sciences. They were motivated by gaining a better understanding of the processes and environmental applications related to LULC and the connection to the research world. One of the students originated from the study area. These students did not have any specific training related to LULC, image analysis or aerial photograph-interpretation and were not experts in LULC.
Administrative staff from IGN	This group comprised two staff from IGN, including non-experts in LULC data or geographic data in general

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

- Nine distinct small-scale campaigns/mapathons, led by IGN-FRANCE were conducted to address how crowdsourcing approaches can be used to validate changes detected from satellite image analysis, while enriching authoritative data on LULC. These campaigns used a combination of the Paysages web and mobile application as well as the LACO-Wiki web application.

- ➔ Conflation of citizen contributions on LULC and land change (both actively collected and passively mined) into authoritative databases

The features to be classified are directly derived from the authoritative LULC data whereas changes to be validated are derived from the Change Detection Service produces by LandSense partner GEOVILLE. Both types of data are first validated by different contributors are then used in order to update authoritative LULC data. The proposed workflow is based on data fusion techniques and is described in [D5.5: Operational workflows for integration of citizen-observed data in authoritative systems](#). Local authorities already access the data they produced and use them together with other sources of information to compute indicators about land change and land take.

- ➔ Cost reductions in professional surveying and/or increase in available LULC data that could not be collected within current budgets of public bodies

Cost reduction is an aspect that IGN will analyse by the end of LandSense project. At the same time with the research work IGN done in WP5, IGN is producing a new LULC data for the same area for 2019 by using the traditional process (i.e. generate LC classes from topographic data and orthophoto interpretation for assigning LU classes). The new LULC 2019 is expected to be released in late 2020. The results of the workflow will be compared with the LULC 2019 data produced in the traditional way. In the same time, the costs of the two approaches (citizen-observed data integration versus traditional mapping) will be evaluated.

→ Open access to improved public information on land take and land change

The collected data (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3691827>) is freely available in the LandSense Zenodo Community repository. Moreover, local authorities already access the data they produced and use them together with other sources of information to compute indicators about land change and land take.

Engagement strategies within the reporting period (steps undertaken to create awareness of the campaign including timeline)

The strategy defined was based on the idea that the contributors should be involved in the process from the beginning. Thus, an initial meeting to define their needs was held. Then, the IGN team defined a series of campaigns, each one having a goal and a target. Then, these campaigns and tools to be used are validated with the contributors and a timeline was defined by taking into account both LandSense and contributors' schedules.

Figure 12: Contributors using Paysages web application to classify authoritative LULC data

During 2019 we organised a series of mapathons focused on two topics: change validation and LU classification.

- Mapathon 1: Experts in LULC from the local authorities (AuAT), January 9 2019, Toulouse
- Mapathon 2: IGN staff, during August 2019
- Mapathon 3: First year students of the National Engineering in GIS School (ENSG), February 1st 2019
- Mapathon 4: First year students of the National Engineering in GIS School (ENSG), February 5, 2019
- Mapathon 5: November 6 2019, Noisy-Champs, France
- Mapathon 6: December 16 2019, Noisy-Champs, France
- Mapathon 7: IGN staff, during September 2019
- Mapathon 8: AuAT (Local Authorities), September 29 2020, Toulouse
- Mapathon 9: AuAT (Local Authorities), January 9 2020, Toulouse

Overview of app/prototype - technical and content related changes during reporting time

PAYSAGES is a [mobile application](#) that guides you to different locations marked on the map in a step-by-step fashion. At each location, you are asked to fill in information about different features in the landscape and take photographs. For example, how is this building being used? Is this area agricultural or residential? Is this quarry active? Has this area changed? By providing this information, you are helping us improve the data about our changing landscapes.

Figure 13: Screenshots from the PAYSAGES mobile application tool

Volunteers can also contribute to the demonstration pilot via the Paysages [web application](#) to validate changes detected by the LandSense change detection service. For example, in the figure below the the polygon represents a change detected by the CDS; the background layer is the orthophoto from 2016 (on the left); the polygon represents a change detected by the CDS; the background layer is Pléiades orthophoto from 2019 (on the right).

Figure 14: Paysages web application interface: the polygon represents a change detected by the change detection service. Underlying photos show change from 2016 to 2019.

Figure 15: Example of changes polygons edited by experts: the orthophoto in 2016 (left), Pléiades in 2019 (middle) and edited polygons with their land use classification (right). Such contributions are valuable for enriching authoritative LULC data

Uptake & Performance Measures

Table 6 Key Performance Indicators: Toulouse

Indicator	During 2019	Planned
Number of installs (mobile)	50+	50
Number of users	131	50-100
Number of observations: change validation task	100% (654/654); multiple validations available for the 654 changes (in total 4200 observations)	80%
Number of observations: LULC classification task	74% (6568/8900);	80%
Photos	463	

2.4 City of Heidelberg

Objective: Demonstrate how citizen-contributed data and Earth Observation (EO) data can update authoritative databases with a strong focus on improving data/map quality

Tools: [OSMlanduse](#) and [LACO-Wiki](#)

Lead: UHEI

Key Stakeholders: City of Heidelberg

Augmentation and cost reduction of authoritative data through citizen science is a key aspect for LandSense specially to complement authoritative land use and land cover related information. This pilot produced a land use prototype based on Corine legend leveraged from OpenStreetMap (OSM) available on [osmlanduse.org](#). The land use product was further refined for the LandSense pilot cities of Heidelberg, Toulouse and Vienna. During the course of the project those sites with increased attention subsequently were extended. In 2018 Geneva was added, analysis for Toulouse was refined using very high-resolution data and specific building classification. Additionally, research was performed to improve mapping accuracy and further extension.

The LandSense pilot OSMlanduse validation provided estimations of map accuracy for the osmlanduse.org product. From the last reporting period from 04-11-2019 (D4.1 Demo 1: Cost reduction and data conflation in monitoring land change I) three additional mapathons were carried out where validation activities were extended to polygon validation of land use features. Through a special download form available at <https://data.osmlanduse.org>, dissemination of our activities land use products were delivered. Direct e-mail request and queries on the implementation of the web mapping service and extraction of OSMlanduse data were coordinated via e-mail and human interaction processes.

As a result of our pilot activities the suitability of land use information provided by OSM was estimated and class appropriate for use identified, namely: urban residential, industrial, agricultural and forest classes. Certain OSM land use classes are an appropriate representation of reality and can be used as a reliable land use estimate for authoritative, commercial and operational use. OSM

Target Groups – update

Target group of contributors are university students, target group for users of osmlanduse is any institution that uses land use information such as governments, companies or NGOs.

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS

- Three additional mapathons were performed two Heidelberg mapathons with academic staff: Toulouse buildings campaign and validation campaign of southern Europe and an eternal DLR/Uni Jena campaign where polygons were validated for Heidelberg
- 40+ deliveries of OSMlanduse product for usage on global application. Among users: the economist newspaper (article on green livability of top 140 international cities), planet labs for deep learning applications, research and NGOs working on Brazilian land use and multiple request for extracts of China and India among many other specific request
- This demonstration pilot helped to build trust in OSMlanduse products as accuracy information on class suitability was produced

- Further deep learning application were fostered promoting the use of OSMLanduse polygons as labels for deep learning activities
- An additional 15k+ reference points for the validation of osmlanduse.org and implemented via a [mapthon](#)
- First successful large area fusion of OSM and Copernicus at 10m spatial resolution or higher, where we acknowledged varying label noise and feature space quality, scales and effective use of artificial intelligence and computing. Our method solely relies on openly available data streams and does not depend on additional expert knowledge.

Engagement strategies within the reporting period (steps undertaken to create awareness of the campaign including timeline)

- 09.2018: Demonstration mapathon at EuroGEOSS Workshop in Geneva
- 01.2019: Land Classification and Monitoring seminar in Heidelberg
- 07.2019: Reference data collection campaign organized jointly with German Aerospace Center and University of Jena
- 08.2019: Reference data collection campaign with University of Münster
- 10.2020: Mapathon as part of European Week of Regions and Cities
- 11. 2020: Mapathon as part of EuroSDR Workshop

Figure 16: Participants of polygon-based validation in Jena organized jointly organized by DLR and University of Jena

Overview of app/prototype - technical and content related changes during reporting time

OSM data and Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite images were combined to derive land use and land cover (LULC) for a large area in Europe using state-of-the-art Deep Learning (DL) technologies. Training data was synthesized

by deriving a classification from OSM features similar to Corine Land Cover (CLC) level 2 and in parts complemented with S2 images from the meteorological summer of 2018. Data preparation, setup and training enables the application of a Fully Convolutional Network (FCN), using the Python Deep Learning library Keras and the Machine Learning (ML) platform Tensorflow. Once trained, the FCN was applied in an automated workflow to produce LULC maps with 10m spatial resolution and temporal and spatial flexibility. Results were subjected to an accuracy assessment and achieve overall accuracies of 62.2% for the study area and 82.9% for a small reference area. However, individual class performances varied largely in terms of map proportions and estimated classification accuracy. Figure 16 outlines the workflow of the new land use product produced.

Figure 17: Development process for new improved land use product

Uptake & Performance Measures

Table 7 Key performance indicators Heidelberg

Indicator	Current	Planned
Number of installs	NA- Deployed in webform	-
Number of testers/users	132	> 120
Number of observations	>15000	> 12000
Points covered by user	~110.3 in average per user	Keep it stable

Key Results

Besides offering point-based validation campaign additionally a polygon-based validation campaign was rolled out to allow detailed comparison of high-quality land use information. Additionally, we scaled up validation exercise to a large region in Europe in preparation of our future activities. Leveraging our methodology of point-based validation campaign to area covering polygon was a key achievement as it

allowed us to produce insights on detailed area specific statistics. Osmlanduse data was compared to the reference data set produced in Jena and extensively compared to the reference dataset (Ground Truth) strengths and weaknesses of Osmlanduse were reported. Although findings and phenomena are only partly applicable to the complete study area, they can still provide valuable hints towards shortcomings and challenges of the respective classification. Figure 18 suggests a strong similarity between ground truth (upper left) and underlying OSM data, whereby sporadic data gaps are visible for the OSM-based classification (upper right). The prediction of the UNet classifier from the first training (lower left) shows a low level of detail and lacks class variance. In addition, this classification is interspersed with artefacts and inaccuracies at class boundaries. In contrast to that, the UNet classifier after the second training (lower right) provides a higher level of detail and class variance. The granularity of the classification has improved visibly, whereas classification impurities decreased within the reference area.

Figure 18: Comparison between different classification attempts (bottom) where the reference data collected during the June 2019 DLR Jena mapathon and the original osmlanduse.org data for Heidelberg’s Schwetzingen suburb

Figure 19 highlights differences between ground truth data (reference dataset) and two selected classifications. The first one is the classification derived from OSM data using legend harmonization, the other one is predicted by the UNet after the second training. Grey areas show an agreement between classifications, whereby other colours reveal the respective class assignment for areas of disagreement.

Figure 19: Reference dataset vs OSM data and vs. classification of the UNet model after the second training. Coloured areas show differences through the class assignment in the respective dataset, whereas grey colour indicates areas of agreement.

Ground truth and OSM classification visibly disagree for agricultural and infrastructural areas (Figure 19). A large part of the data gaps in the OSM classification (upper right) appears to correspond with the class Industrial, commercial and transport units (1.2) in the reference dataset (upper left). The prediction of the

classifier (lower right) in comparison to the reference dataset (lower left) shows the strongest discrepancy at the borders of the UNet classification, resulting in outline effects at the edges of classes. To be able to quantify the level and direction of disagreement and between classifications with great detail, two confusion matrixes are employed. Comparing ground truth and OSM classifications an agreement of 77.4% between the two classifications can be observed. The OSM classification shows a no data proportion of 7.9% for the whole area, while its largest proportion (36.1%) is assigned to Industrial, commercial and transport units (1.2) in the reference dataset. Overall best performing classes with over 90% agreement are Urban fabric (1.1), Industrial, commercial and transport units (1.2), Mine, dump and construction sites (1.3) and Forests (3.1). Accuracy is lower than 15% for classes Pastures (2.3), Shrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations (3.2), Open spaces with little or no vegetation (3.3) and Inland wetlands (4.1). However, when considering class proportions, less than 1% of the area is classified as Open spaces with little or no vegetation (3.3) or Inland wetlands (4.1) in the reference dataset (see Appendix). The OSM classification shows the highest absolute disagreement for class Arable land (2.1). Here, an overestimation of 5.8% relates to the class Pastures (2.3) and is clearly visible in the left side of Figure 19. Class Urban fabric (1.1) is also overestimated in the OSM classification and relates to class 1.2 (3.6%) and 1.4 (2.4%). Other areas of disagreement often appear as fragments at the very edges of continuous classifications like rivers, residential areas and streets. Misclassification is common in the context of small-scale structures like standalone buildings inside large continuous areas (Figure 19). If gaps present in the OSM classification are disregarded for the calculation of accuracy measures, OA reaches 83% inside the reference area.

Abundance of OSM data, size, distinct features and urban properties were found to be strong factors to why classification accuracy was much better within the reference area. In both maps, strong confusion was found between agricultural areas (classes 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3). Consequentially, merging those could increase overall accuracy of resulting maps but also reduces thematic depth. Also, a connection between small class proportions and low accuracy values could be derived. This indicates that the amount of data required to successfully train small LULC classes is inversely proportional to the amount of data provided by OSM features, where small classes are often surrounded by gaps. Thus, improving quantity and quality of underlying training data can be identified as a key objective to create more accurate classifications in future works. Other potential measures include using more spectral bands or adding band indices, reworking the translation of OSM values into LULC classes and introducing post-processing methods. Also, multiple specialized classifiers could be employed to address classes individually.

Although this work does not reach quality levels of regional, tailor-made LULC products, it supports the fast and simple generation of LULC information for any given region, provided that enough OSM features are present. It also allows the generation of LULC maps, while considering seasonality, variable input dimensions and cloud cover.

3 Conclusions

This deliverable provides a detailed overview of the four demonstration pilots (Vienna, Amsterdam, Toulouse, Heidelberg) within the Urban Landscapes Dynamics theme in LandSense. Descriptions of target groups, data types, methodologies and engagement approaches help to distinguish the various pilots. The pilots guarantee open access to the datasets to promote sustainability and further exploitation by relevant citizen science and earth observation communities. The data for the [Vienna](#), [Amsterdam](#) and [Toulouse](#) examples is already accessible in the [LandSense Zenodo Community](#) and publication of the Heidelberg dataset is pending.